

ACOUSTIC EMISSION AS AN AID FOR

INSPECTING GFRP PRESSURE TUBES

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Glass-fiber-reinforced plastics (GFRP) are increasingly being used for highly stressed structural elements. The higher the demands on the materials, the higher are the fault detection requirements to be met by non-destructive materials testing methods. Acoustic emission (AE) is a valuable aid for the non-destructive inspection of anisotropic inhomogeneous materials such as GFRP.

The usefulness of AE for detecting and evaluating defects in the material at loads far below the ultimate stress limit of fault-free specimens has been demonstrated on GFRP pressure tubes with deliberately produced defects.

Causes of AE and Measuring Methods

AE analysis is based on the phenomenon that the sudden release of elastic energy in solid materials under load results in the emission of acoustic pulses. The major causes of AE are deformation processes as well as crack formation and crack propagation; AE additionally results from friction processes in the material. The frequencies of AE extend far into the ultrasonic region, and from this spectrum frequencies between 50 kHz and 1.5 MHz are of practical use for inspection measurements. At higher frequencies the attenuation in the material renders AE too weak and at lower frequencies the extraneous interfering noise is usually too strong. Since the sensitivity of measurements increases with decreasing frequencies, it is desirable to make the measurements at the lowest frequencies possible in view of the interfering noise.

There are two kinds of AE to be distinguished (Fig. 1):

- burst signals, which are discrete events caused by crack formation, crack propagation (due to fiber failure and inter-fiber failure in GFRP) and small-area friction processes (e.g. stick slip); and

a)

b)

Fig. 1: The two types of acoustic emission
 a) burst signals; b) continuous AE

- continuous AE where separate acoustic signals are not perceived. This type of AE, which is caused by homogeneous deformation processes, large-area friction and extensive microcracking with a rapid succession of pulses ($>10^3/s$), is not observed in GFRP.

Cracking processes in GFRP are characterized by burst signals which result in individual peaks in the oscillograph trace at low time resolution. At higher time resolution, however, it is found that the signals consist of a multitude of transient peaks caused by the multiple reflections of the acoustic pulses in the specimen or structural element. At even higher time resolution the single oscillations of the transducer are visible. In the case of fiber and inter-fiber failures the total duration of a burst signal is of the order of milliseconds.

AE usually is recorded with the aid of piezoelectric transducers which transform acoustic pulses into electric voltage pulses. These voltage pulses are subsequently amplified and, when resonant transducers are used, filtered at

resonant frequencies and processed further. This simple measuring setup is shown in the lower part of Fig. 2. The signals are recorded on magnetic tape for subsequent analysis, and for their evaluation all oscillations exceeding a pre-selectable discriminator threshold are counted on-line during the experiment or later, from a tape recorder. This yields the so-called total AE count, which is the measure of AE intensity. Comparison of the total AE counts or AE count rates at different threshold levels, i.e. amplitude distribution analysis provides additional information about the failure mode, viz. fiber failure or inter-fiber failure. Both failure mechanisms result in burst signals whose amplitude distribution may be described by

$$I = I_0 \cdot D^{-n}, \quad (1)$$

where I is the count rate; D is the threshold level; and n and I_0 are positive constants.

Investigations on GFRP laminates with notches of different depths have shown that the exponent n in the above equation enables the two failure mechanisms to be distinguished [1/ 2/]: for inter-fiber failure we have $n_{if} \geq 1.15$ and for fiber failure $n_f \leq 0.8$. The exponent n decreases as the energy released in the fracture process increases. In the case of crack propagation there is usually a superposition of acoustic pulses originating from different microcracking mechanisms which leads to scatter of the exponent n . If both of the above-identified mechanisms occur at the same time, the most energetic - i.e. fiber failure - predominates.

In addition to single-channel integral AE measurements with a single transducer, it is possible to use several transducers for determining delay time differences. At a given characteristic wave propagation velocity in the material the geometric location of the AE source can be derived. When using at least two transducers linear location between the transducers is feasible, i.e. the location of the AE source is projected on to the connecting line between the transducers. The flaw locations lie on hyperbolas in the focuses of which the two transducers are arranged lengthwise on the tube. To avoid erroneous measurements a third transducer usually is placed in the middle between the two others. Electric interference causes all the transducers to respond at the same time and can be eliminated. Fig. 2 (upper half) shows the measuring setup for multi-channel linear flaw location in addition to that for single-channel AE measurements.

Linear flaw location experiments were performed on tubes 1235 mm in length which were subdivided into three identical measuring sections. The signals of the various transducers (170 kHz) were amplified and filtered and passed into a 32-channel location system (Dunegan-Endevco) for on-line indications of flaw locations.

Wave propagation in GFRP is anisotropic, which is to be attributed to the different wave velocities in the matrix and the fibers and the multiple reflections of the acoustic pulses

Fig. 2: Schematic representation of the measuring setup for combined internal pressure tests and AE measurements on GFRP tubes

at the fiber-matrix interfaces. According to Reynolds et al. /3/ the velocity in unidirectionally fiber-reinforced plastics ranges between 1.8 and 2.4 m/ms. In the experimental GFRP pressure tubes the wave velocity in axial direction was about 2 m/ms (Fig. 3) as found with ultrasonic test signals. This figure additionally shows the measured delay times.

Amplitude attenuation in the direction of the reinforcing fibers is less pronounced than normal to them. In Fig. 3 this is reflected in the amplitude maximums at a distance of 140 mm, which corresponds to the winding pattern of the rovings. There is an overall exponential attenuation of the signal with increasing distance between source and sensor, which means that within the distance of 350 mm between the outer transducers for a measuring section the amplitudes decreased by a factor of 2. Location accuracy was about 5 percent of the distance between transducers.

Test Program and Objectives

GFRP tubes about 1200 mm long, with an inside diameter of 75 mm and a wall thickness of 9 mm (nine double filament layers, winding angle 60°) were inspected at an internal pressure of up to 200 bar, which corresponds to about 15 percent of the bursting pressure of faultless tubes. In addition, 400 mm long sections of the same tubes were subjected to AE measurements until bursting. Part of the tubes were fault-free while others had deliberately produced defects. The various types of defects included:

- a) localized defects
 - concealed cuts in the tube wall
 - knotted rovings
 - missing rovings (defect recurring over the entire tube length in accordance with the winding pattern)
 - damage by impact load
- b) non-localized defects
 - unimpregnated layers
 - flexibilized resin
 - glass fibers of excessively low Young's modulus

- The AE measurements were carried out in order to
- identify defective tubes at a test pressure of about 15 percent of the bursting pressure (about 200 bar),
 - provide approximate information on the significance of the defect at the above test pressure and the resulting reduction of the bursting pressure, and
 - determine the approximate location of the defect.

Results

In order to differentiate localized from non-localized defects the geometric location of the AE source was determined by measuring the time differences of the signals arriving at various transducers, taking as a basis the experimentally identified wave velocity of 2 m/ms. At the measuring frequency of 170 kHz and with the above-described location system on-line

Fig. 3 : Wave propagation velocity and attenuation in CFRP tubes (winding 137.6 mm)

Fig. 4: Linear location (CRT scope)

determination of the AE source location is feasible. Fig. 4 shows the locations determined at the experimental pressure stage of 125 to 200 bar on a tube with concealed cut; the location of the cut is obvious.

When plotting the number of locations at the various pressure stages versus the measuring section on the connecting line between transducers it is found that the activity of the defect increases as the pressure increases. To demonstrate this, a tube with a concealed cut was tested at pressures up to 560 bar, which corresponds to about 50 percent of the bursting pressure of a fault-free tube. As can be seen in Fig. 5 the majority of signals originated in the region of the concealed cut. At lower pressures the scatter of locations depends only on the locating accuracy, whereas at higher pressures the defective area expands as a result of delamination, which leads to a wider scatter of locations. Using transmitted light the growth of the delaminated zone becomes evident at pressures above, say, 200 to 300 bar. When plotting the number of locations versus the axial measuring section it is found that this number in the region of the concealed cut strongly increases as the test pressure rises. This indicates an increase in the crack surfaces forming per unit time.

Non-localized defects are uniformly distributed over the whole tube length, which means that AE source location yields a uniform pattern along the tube. Since the defects may be of microscopic size the energy emitted during their growth as well as the portion of energy transformed into acoustic signals are so low that location of these defects is possible only at relatively high pressures. The total AE count recorded by one transducer, on the other hand, increases already at low internal pressures because of the large volume of defective material. This increase in the total AE count for a tube with non-localized defects differs characteristically from that for a non-defective tube. Non-localized defects are indicated at low pressure (cf. Fig. 7) at which non-defective tubes do not show irreversible changes in the material.

Fig. 5: Number of locations versus axial measuring section, on a tube with concealed cut

Non-defective tubes and tubes with a small volume of defective material, i.e. with low-volume localized defects such as knotted rovings do not show characteristic variations either of the total AE count or the bursting pressure. For tubes with non-localized defects distributed over their whole length (e.g. missing rovings), on the other hand, the total AE count at low pressures is considerably higher than for fault-free tubes; in addition, the bursting pressure of this kind of tubes is about 15 percent lower than that of fault-free tubes.

Therefore the significance of localized and non-localized defects in GFRP tubes must be evaluated by different methods:

- Localized defects are exactly located at a test pressure corresponding to about 15 percent of the bursting pressure of fault-free tubes, and their significance can be evaluated on the basis of the number of AE locations related to the measuring section.

- Non-localized defects are detected by integral measurement of AE as total AE count by only one transducer. These defects are detected at a test pressure of about 15 percent of the bursting pressure.

Figs. 6 and 7 show the measuring results for defective tubes which were subjected to a pressure test in order to determine the reduction in bursting pressure in percent. The bursting pressure determined on the 400 mm long tube sections is plotted versus the internal pressure above which definite fault detection through AE is possible. Fig. 6 relates to fault detection through AE source location while Fig. 7 relates to the total AE count, a distinct increase in which indicates the presence of defects. The significance level (decreases in bursting pressure below 9.5 percent were considered insignificant because these are within the normal limits for fault-free tubes) and the test pressure (about 15 percent of the bursting pressure of fault-free tubes) are also shown.

Fig. 6 shows which defects can be definitely located above specific internal pressures with the aid of AE. Strictly localized defects which lead to a high bursting pressure decrease, e.g. concealed cuts through two or more layers or damage by impact load can be located at a very low pressure. Concealed cuts through a single layer in a low-stress zone and knotted rovings merely produce a reduction of the bursting pressure below the significance level and are detected at pressures above the test pressure.

Non-localized defects such as missing rovings reduce the bursting pressure of the tube considerably but can be detected only at relatively high internal pressures through AE source location. Other non-localized defects such as unimpregnated layers and polyester resin (instead of epoxy resin) lead to scattered source locations at very low pressures.

However, when using the total AE count as an additional aid to fault detection (cf. Fig. 7) it is found that even all non-localized defects causing a significant decrease in bursting pressure, e.g. unimpregnated layers, polyester resin (instead of epoxy resin), E-glass (instead of S-glass fibres) are

Fig. 6: Bursting pressure decrease versus the pressure above which defects can be located by AE (↓ leakage of the system; bursting pressure decrease is lower)

Fig. 7: Bursting pressure decrease versus the pressure above which defects are indicated by a distinct increase in the total AE count (↓ leakage of the system; bursting pressure decrease is lower)

recorded already at low pressures, i.e. below the test pressure. This is also true (with one exception) for tubes with missing rovings, as becomes obvious when comparing Figs. 6 and 7. However, it should be noted that in some cases (indicated by arrows) the decrease in bursting pressure depicted in Figs. 6 and 7 is too high because in these tests the packing rings were destroyed before the tube failed. Therefore the actual bursting pressure decrease was not determined, but it was certainly lower than the plotted value. In accordance with this, the presence of defects was indicated by the total AE count only at high pressures. Knotted rovings causing a high bursting pressure decrease can also be detected by total AE count at the test pressure. Contrary to non-localized defects strictly localized defects such as a concealed cut or damage by impact load are indicated by total AE count only at relatively high pressures.

Amplitude distribution analysis of the acoustic signals determined on the various defective tubes indicated only inter-fiber failure up to the test pressure of about 200 bar, which means that below this pressure the fiber structure was not damaged and the strength of the experimental tubes therefore was not reduced.

The following conclusions may be drawn from these investigations: To be able to classify the defects clearly with respect to their significance and size, both AE parameters - location and total AE count - must be determined. When recording exclusively the total AE count it is impossible to distinguish between strictly localized significant defects such as concealed cuts, and less significant non-localized defects, e.g. flexibilized resin, because the intensity of AE in the two cases is comparable. On the other hand, the example of the missing rovings shows that defect location alone is also insufficient to assess the significance of all defects (cf. Figs. 6 and 7). Using both parameters, it is possible to identify specimens with significant defects at test pressures up to about 15 percent of the bursting pressure and assess the significance of the defects.

References

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